

Appendix 1

Keyword Dictionary

Pillar	Keywords
Environmental	carbon, emission, greenhouse gas, ghg, renewable, clean energy, energy efficiency, solar, wind power, electric vehicle, ev, hybrid, low-carbon, decarbonization, carbon neutral, net zero, packaging recycling, recyclable, waste reduction, circular economy, green logistics, sustainable packaging, carbon footprint, scope 1, scope 2, scope 3
Social	employee, staff, worker, training, development, safety, occupational health, ohs, community, diversity, inclusion, gender, labor rights, fair wage, employee benefit, welfare, union, human rights, supply chain labor, customer satisfaction, product safety
Governance	board of directors, independent director, audit, compliance, transparency, disclosure, ethics, code of conduct, anti-corruption, bribery, whistleblowing, risk management, internal control, shareholder, executive compensation, esg committee, sustainability committee
